

Fatigue life of S960 high strength steel with laser cladDED functional surface layers

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Abstract

This study evaluates the fatigue life of S960 high-strength steel with laser-cladDED layers of aluminium bronze, hard chrome, cobalt alloy, and stainless steel, using three-point bending tests. Our results demonstrate that while these cladDED layers offer potential for enhanced surface properties, they generally reduce the material's fatigue life due to alterations in the heat-affected zone and the introduction of microstructural defects at layer interfaces. The extent of fatigue life reduction varies with the type of cladDED layer, highlighting the importance of optimizing laser cladDED parameters to minimize detrimental effects and improve component longevity.

Keywords: Laser cladDED; S960 high strength steel; Aluminium-bronze; Hardchrome; Cobalt alloy; Stainless steel; Fatigue life

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1. Introduction

Contemporary requirements on functional surfaces of highly mechanically loaded components lead to the use of parts that are manufactured by a combination of different metallic materials. The components usually consist of a base material to which a relatively thin functional layer of additional material is applied, which gives better functional and protective properties to a product, see e.g. [1][2]

Laser cladDED, the technology used in the production of bi-material components, is a relatively new but increasingly used method that finds application in many industrial areas [3][4][5][6]. The method is suitable for both creating functional surfaces with specific properties and for carrying out high quality repairs of worn parts. With a right choice of material combinations and process parameters, the laser cladDED technology can effectively replace some older technologies, which are moreover often problematic from a health or environmental point of view.

The principle of the method of the laser cladDED, Fig. 1, is based on a heat process in which a metal wire or powder mixed with an inert gas is fed into a laser beam where the material is melted down together with a base material and a deposition layer is formed on a surface of substrate.

Fig. 1. Laser cladding; (a) the principle of laser cladding and (b) applying a thin cobalt layer to a S960 steel using the laser cladding.

One of the advantages of the laser cladding method is a relatively low temperature impact on the whole cladded parts, i.e. relatively low thermal influence on the base material, and thus a lower risk of thermal deformation. Other advantages are a high process stability even at high cladding speeds, possibility to select a chemical composition of additive materials and a relatively easy automation of process.

Suitably applied surface layer can provide the required properties of the product (hardness, abrasion resistance, wear resistance, surface corrosion resistance, etc.). On the other hand, its application on the base material influences the surface layer of the base material due to the thermal effect during cladding. In the heat-affected zone (HAZ) the microstructure and the corresponding mechanical properties of the base material are altered [7] [8]. Moreover, a narrow transition zone is formed by a mixture of the base and the added material in the molten area. These issues are significant also in the case of cladded components made of high strength steels. Inhomogeneities in the material structure of the laser cladded layer and thermally influenced transition zone are important issues from the point of view of mechanical properties of laser cladded components. Inhomogeneities include local changes of microstructure related to the hardness, cracks, craters, pores, bubbles and inclusions [5][9][10]. These defects are caused by many circumstances such as a chemical composition of the substrate or additive material, moisture, impurities, inappropriate choice of cladding parameters or failure in controlling of technological discipline (e.g. insufficient preheating, high cooling speed). Very harmful defects from the point of view of fatigue strength include small cracks of a technological nature, so-called hot cracks, which may initiate in the area of superheated material adjoining to the fusion zone immediately during the cladding process and subsequent cooling. In addition to the structural properties, the strength and durability of bi-material elements created by the laser cladding process is also influenced by the level of intrinsic stress. The intrinsic stress arises in the material during cooling or is generated in the areas of macrodefects [11][12].

Structural elements or components processed by laser cladding technology are very often subjected to time-varying loads during their functional life. An example of such a component is a forming mandrel used in deep drawing or rotary draw bending process [13][14]. Repeated loading causes microscopic damage of a material resulting in initiation of fatigue cracks and propagation of existing microcracks and finally fracture of the component. The fatigue life is affected by many factors including parameters of the cyclic loading, quality of surface, grain size, temperature, residual stress state, structural defects, welding or cladding technology or presence of corrosive environment. In the case of materials processed by laser cladding technology, there is also the issue of material interfaces that affect the initiation and propagation of fatigue cracks [15]. An example of a bi-material interface between S960 steel and hard chrome layer with heat affected zone of the base material is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Example of bi-material interface; specimen made of high strength steel S960 with a hard chrome layer [1] [2] surface laser clad layers; [3] heat affected zone.

This paper presents experimental results and discussion of fatigue life of high strength steel S960 laser-clad by four types of functional surface layers. The fatigue life was experimentally determined by three-point bending test and the results are expressed by S-N curves. The fatigue life was discussed based on observation of defects on the fracture surfaces.

Nomenclatures

HAZ	Heat Affected Zone
E	Young's Modulus
f	Load Frequency
N_f	Number of Cycles to Fracture
A, B	Material Constants in Basquin Equation
P_a	Amplitude of the Loading Force
R	Stress Ratio
R^2	Index of Dispersion
σ_a	Stress Amplitude
ν	Poisson's Ratio
P	Laser Power
v	Feed Rate
l	Side Shift
Q_1	Process Gas Flow Rate
Q_2	Shielding Gas Flow Rate

2. Materials and specimens

High-strength steel S960 was chosen as the base material for the production of the samples, see properties during the fatigue load [16], changes of the properties due to HAZ [17] and the variation of the temperature [18][19]. Thin surface layers of either Metco 51NS aluminium bronze, Rockit 401 hard chromium, Höganäs 316L stainless steel or cobalt alloy were applied to this base material by the laser cladding method. The materials parameters are given in Tab. 1.

Table 1. Basic parameters of material of the base material and laser-cladded layers.

Designation	Description	E [GPa]	ν [-]	Hardness HV 0.5	Type
S960	High strength steel	202	0.27	346	base material
Metco 51NS	Aluminum bronze	117	0.32	158	laser-cladded layer
Rockit 401	Hard chrome	104	0.22	620	laser-cladded layer
Höganäs 316L	Stainless steel	193	0.25	155	laser-cladded layer
---	Cobalt alloy	214	0.27 – 0.30	440	laser-cladded layer

Two surface layers were cladded to a rolled S960 steel plates with dimensions 300×200×20 mm and a surface roughness Ra 1.6 using a robotic laser cladding device MLHW-4000. The direction of cladding was parallel to the direction of rolling of the base material, Fig. 3. The parameters of deposition process are given in Tab. 2.

Table 2. Parameters of deposition process.

Power	Feed rate	Side shift	Process gas flow rate	Shielding gas flow rate	Gas
P [W]	v [cm/min]	l [mm]	Q_1 [l/min]	Q_2 [l/min]	[-]
1050 – 1200	28 – 35	1.1 – 1.4	10	12	Argon 5.0

Fig. 3. Applied surface layers; A – hard chrome, B – cobalt alloy, C – stainless steel, D – aluminum bronze; red arrows - rolling direction/cladding direction; blue arrows - material cutting direction.

The samples for three-point bending tests were cut out from cladded plates perpendicularly to the cladding direction and machined to final dimensions of 5.5 × 21 × 100 mm, Fig. 4. The total coating thicknesses on base material applied in two cladded layers were between 1 and 2 mm after surface machining. The final surface roughness Ra was 0.4.

Fig. 4. Specimens for fatigue tests consist of steel substrate S960 coated with; (a) aluminium bronze layer, (b) cobalt alloy, (c) hard chrome layer and (d) stainless steel.

X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (XRF spectrometry) was performed with the Delta Professional handheld spectrometer to identify the actual chemical composition of the cladded layers [20]. The results for each coating material are shown in Tabs. 3-6.

Table 3. Chemical composition of the aluminium bronze layer Metco 51NS.

Parameter	Unit	Chemical elements									
		Cu	Al	Fe	Si	Cr	Mn	C	Mo	Ni	V
Declared content	[%]	Bal.	8.50 – 10.80	0.50 – 2.00	–	–	–	0.15	–	–	–
Real content	[%]	68.50	23.84	5.24	1.78	0.28	0.20	–	0.05	0.03	0.08

Table 4. Chemical composition of the hard chrome layer Rockit 401.

Parameter	Unit	Chemical elements						
		Fe	Cr	Ni	Si	Mo	Mn	V
Declared content	[%]	Bal.	18.00	2.50	–	0.50	–	–
Real content	[%]	78.83	17.22	2.05	1.04	0.49	0.15	0.22

Table 5. Chemical composition of the stainless-steel layer Höganäs 316L.

Parameter	Unit	Chemical elements						
		Fe	Cr	Ni	Mn	Mo	Si	Cu
Declared content	[%]	Bal.	16.00 – 18.00	12.00 – 14.00	0.20	2.00 – 3.00	0.50 – 1.00	–
Real content	[%]	79.45	9.15	7.55	1.30	1.14	0.93	0.16

Table 6. Chemical composition of the cobalt alloy layer.

Parameter	Unit	Chemical elements							
		Co	Cr	Fe	W	Ni	Cu	Mn	Mo
Declared content	[%]	Bal.	27.50 – 29.50	0.90 – 1.30	4.00 – 4.80	3.00	–	–	–
Real content	[%]	54.42	25.33	13.92	3.98	1.00	0.73	0.29	0.24

The declared content of chemical elements determines the chemical composition of the used cladding powder. The real content then indicates the actual content of the chemical elements in the created cladded layer. The differences are caused by the applied technology and set parameters of cladding and possible deviations of measurements. Regarding the used method, it is necessary to mention that the elements with atomic numbers from 1 to 11 are not detectable by this method.

3. Three-point bending fatigue test

To assess the impact of the laser cladded layers on the fatigue life of components made from the high strength steel S960 three-point bending tests were applied. The specimen dimensions and orientation of the cladded layer with respect to the loading is shown in Fig. 5. The tests were performed on the Roell Amsler 20 HFP 5100 resonant pulsator. The specimens were placed in the test device grips so that the cladded layers were subjected to a cyclic bending tensile stress. The cycle asymmetry parameter (stress ratio) was chosen to be $R = 0.1$. This stress ratio is often used in components testing in many industries (primarily in aviation, automotive but also in forming especially in deep drawing, see [21]) and corresponds to a tension-tension cycle.

The loading frequency f at the beginning of cycling was about 100 Hz, the effect of frequency influence is mentioned e.g. in [22]. The tests were performed in laboratory air at temperature $21 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and a humidity of approximately 40 %. The specimens were loaded by constant force amplitude P_a , resulting in a stress amplitude σ_a on the specimen surface. After crack initiation with increasing crack length the loading frequency of the resonant fatigue machine decreased due to decreasing stiffness of the specimen. The tests were interrupted when the loading frequency decreased by 40 Hz. When this condition was reached, the propagation of the fatigue crack was already so fast that only a negligible number of loading cycles remained until the final fracture of the test body. For this reason, the number of cycles at a frequency drop of 40 Hz was taken as the number of cycles corresponding to the fracture N_f .

The influence of the laser cladded layers on the lifetime was characterized by Wöhler curves (S-N curves) defined as the dependence of the number of cycles to fracture N_f on the stress amplitude σ_a .

Fig. 5. Three-point bending test scheme; all dimensions are in mm

4. Results

4.1. Influence of surface layers on fatigue life

Experimentally determined dependences of the number of cycles to fracture on the stress amplitude for stress the ratio $R = 0.1$ are presented in Fig. 6. The arrows at experimental points indicate specimens which did not fail after application of 10^7 cycles (run out specimens).

Fig. 6. Dependence of the number of cycles N_f on the stress amplitude σ_a for S960 steel, S960 steel with heat affected zone and four different laser cladded layers.

The data for the base material S960 are presented by the black solid squares. Black empty squares represent results of measurement on specimens that originally had a deposited thin aluminium bronze layer on the surface that was fully removed by milling and the surface was finally polished with the same roughness as in the case of testing of the base material. The surface of the specimens on which the initiation of fatigue cracks took place thus consisted of a heat affected zone of S960 material. Though the experimental data exhibit for both cases large scatter it is obvious that the fatigue strength of specimens with HAZ on the surface is in the high cycle region substantially worse than that of the base material. The decrease makes about 40 % for the fatigue life 10^7 cycles.

The experimental points for particular specimens in Fig. 6 were fitted by Basquin equation $\sigma_a = AN_f^B$ and the results are listed in Tab. 7 and presented by lines in Fig. 6.

Application of the aluminium bronze layer on the S960 steel results in fatigue life which is comparable to the behavior of the material from the HAZ. Particularly the fatigue strength for 10^7 cycles is nearly identical, see Tab. 8. Similarly, the material covered by the cobalt alloy layers has the lifetime very close to that of the material from the HAZ. The situation is, however, different when applying stainless steel and hard chrome layers. The fatigue strength is substantially lower, and the effect is increasing toward the high cycle fatigue region. Application of the stainless steel decreases the fatigue strength of the S960 for 10^7 cycles by 64 % and application of hard chrome even by 84 %, see Tab. 8.

Table 7. Basquin equations of the dependence of the number of cycles on the stress amplitude for different cladded materials.

Studied Material combination	Basquin equation	Index of dispersion R^2 [-]
S960-base	$\sigma_a = 686.6 N^{-0.046}$	0.27
S960-HAZ	$\sigma_a = 1276.8 N^{-0.114}$	0.66
S960/aluminium bronze	$\sigma_a = 2735.9 N^{-0.163}$	0.94
S960/Cobalt alloy	$\sigma_a = 1076.8 N^{-0.107}$	0.89
S960/Stainless steel	$\sigma_a = 2957.1 N^{-0.200}$	0.95
S960/Hard chrome	$\sigma_a = 2710.6 N^{-0.245}$	0.97

Table 8. The fatigue strength for $N = 10^7$ cycles for $R = 0.1$.

Material combinations	Fatigue strength σ_c [MPa]
S960-base	328
S960/HAZ	203
S960/aluminium bronze	198
S960/Cobalt alloy	192
S960/Stainless steel	118
S960/Hard chrome	52

4.2. Fatigue fracture analysis

The observation of the fatigue fractures of S960 steel with cladded layers was performed on representative specimens using a scanning electron microscope Tescan LYRA 3 XMU FEG/SEMxFIB.

Fracture surface of specimens with aluminium bronze layers is shown in Fig. 7. It is evident, that there is good connection of the first bronze layer with the heat affected zone of S960 steel, Fig. 7(c). However, the interface between the first and second cladded layer, Fig. 7(d) exhibits an evident lack of fusion between both layers. This is a technological problem of cladding bronze to bronze.

Fig. 7. Fracture surface of S960 steel specimen with aluminium bronze layers/S960.
(a) overview, (b) interface between base material and HAZ, (c) interface between 1st cladded layer and base material, (d) detail of interface between 1st cladded layer and base material, (e) interface between 1st and 2nd cladded layer.

The cobalt layers deposited on S960 steel show very good fusion, Fig. 8. No defects are visible between the base material and between the two deposited layers.

Fig. 8. Fracture surface of S960 steel with cobalt alloy layers (sample ST9/14). (a) overview, (b) base material and two clad layers, (c) interface between 1st clad layer and base material, (d) interface between 1st and 2nd clad layer.

In the case of material combination stainless steel/S960, Fig. 9, there is a low quality of the interface between the heat affected layer of the base material and the first stainless steel layer. There are many defects, discontinuities and oxides along the boundary. From fractographic features can be deduced, that the fatigue crack was initiated at this interface roughly in the middle of the specimen, see Fig. 9(b). Also the quality of the interface between the first and second clad layer is quite poor.

Fig. 9. Fracture surface of S960 steel with stainless steel layers.
(a) overview, (b) interface between 1st cladded layer and base material, (c), (d) interface between 1st and 2nd cladded layer.

In the case of the hard chrome/S960 material combination, Fig. 10, the most critical area is the interface between the first and the second cladded layer. Many defects in fusion in the form of voids, impurities are distributed along the interface. They are sites of multiple fatigue crack initiation.

Fig. 10. Fracture surface of S960 steel with hard chrome layers.

(a) overview, (b) base material and two cladded layers, (c) interface between 1st cladded layer and HAZ of the base material, (d) interface between 1st and 2nd cladded layer.

5. Discussion

For the experimental determination of the fatigue life was chosen three point bending test. This was because the components, like mandrels used in deep drawing [13][14] which are covered by layers which improve their abrasion properties are in practice cyclically loaded, often just in bending. Since their lifetime in the production process is limited due to the wear of the layers, the method of mandrel restoring by deposition of new layers using the laser cladding is both economical and environmentally friendly.

The experimentally determined S-N curves show that the fatigue life of S960 steel with aluminium bronze, cobalt alloy, stainless steel and hard chrome layers applied by laser cladding (under used laser cladding parameters) is lower than that of the base material. Fatigue life reduction increases towards the high-cycle region. The reduction is due to the fact that the laser cladding affects the surface layer of the S960 steel and forms the heat affected zone. Another reason for the reduction in fatigue life is the formation of defects at the interface between the heat-affected zone and the interfaces of the applied layers.

The comparison of the S-N curves indicates that the fatigue life of the S960 steel with the deposited layers of aluminium bronze and cobalt alloy is nearly the same than that of the material in the heat affected zone. The interface between the heat affected zone and cladded layers does not exhibit large defects. Contrary to this, in the case of stainless steel and hard chrome layers, large defects and discontinuities are spread along the layer/heat affected zone interfaces.

From the above presented results it follows that the potential for improving fatigue properties of S960 steel with cladded layers lies in optimization of the laser cladding process parameters resulting in elimination of defects on the layer interfaces.

6. Conclusions

The application of the laser clad layers of aluminium bronze, cobalt alloy, stainless steel and hard chrome reduces the fatigue life of components made from S960 steel.

The laser cladding technology inevitably creates the heat affected zone at the S960 steel, which results in decrease of fatigue life, especially in the high cycle fatigue region. For the fatigue life 10^7 cycles the ratio of the stress amplitudes for heat effected S960 material and base material makes 0.62, i.e. a decrease is about 40 %.

Bronze and cobalt layers clad on the S960 steel have small effect on the fatigue life, which is comparable to that of the material from the heat affected zone. Application of the stainless steel decreases the fatigue strength of the S960 by 64 % and application of hard chrome even by 84 %.

Deterioration of fatigue strength due to application of the clad layers is related to the formation of the heat effected zone of the base material below the clad layers and by the defects which are formed on the interfaces either between the two clad layers or between the heat affected zone and the first clad layer.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Stanislav Seitl reports financial support was provided by Czech Science Foundation and internal competition of Faculty of Civil Engineering, Brno University of Technology.

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